

Integrating stakeholder knowledge to design fair and acceptable climate mitigation and compensation measures in the buildings and mobility sectors in Austria

TransFair-AT Working Paper #3

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Abstract

Identifying and assessing the fairness and acceptability of climate mitigation policies requires not only the application of sound interdisciplinary scientific methods, but also the consideration of stakeholder expertise and values. We applied such an approach to a model analysis of climate mitigation measures and compensation measures for vulnerable households in the buildings and mobility sectors in Austria. We integrated stakeholder knowledge and values by conducting two interactive stakeholder workshops and by a continuous engagement dialogue with a Stakeholder Board (SB) representing key Austrian institutions. The first workshop highlighted: (1) important characteristics to consider for vulnerable households, i.e. households that are likely to be substantially negatively affected by climate mitigation policies; (2) a ranking of both mitigation and compensation measures tailored to the buildings and mobility sectors. We were able to incorporate most of the stakeholders' findings and recommendations into our analysis and the model simulations. The continuous dialogue with the SB ensured the refinement of the implementation of these measures. Finally, the second workshop was used to critically reflect on the results of the model simulations and to highlight blind spots and special cases of hardship which were outside of the modelling framework. The results of the simulated mitigation and compensation policy scenario were generally considered reasonable and fair by the participants. However, further research and surveys are needed to explore the acceptability of the policy packages to decision-makers and the general public.

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1 Introduction

Involving stakeholders in the design of policy mixes for model simulations can significantly enhance the representation of real-world challenges and solutions (Hirsch Hadorn et al., 2006). This is particularly important given the social and political complexities associated with climate policies (Green and Healy, 2022; Williges et al., 2022). Furthermore, stakeholder engagement can help identify and address issues that lie beyond the scope of modeling frameworks (van Dijk et al., 2023).

Recognizing these benefits, we sought to integrate stakeholder knowledge into the research design of the **TransFair-AT** project, which aimed to (1) provide a model-based analysis of the economic and social impacts of a complete decarbonisation of the residential buildings and passenger transport sectors in Austria by 2040, and (2) develop targeted compensation mechanisms to mitigate the burden on particularly vulnerable groups (see Kettner et al., 2025; Kettner-Marx et al., 2021). Our stakeholder knowledge integration process aimed to support these research objectives by:

- incorporating stakeholder insights on:
 - the characteristics of vulnerable households (Bock-Schappelwein and Kettner, 2023, see 2024; Pfaffenbichler et al., 2023), and
 - the effectiveness and fairness of proposed policy measures (see Kettner et al., 2025; Pfaffenbichler et al., 2024); and
- increasing the acceptance of the policy mix when the results are disseminated.

To achieve this, we organized two interactive stakeholder workshops, one at the beginning of the research project to integrate stakeholder knowledge on the definition of decarbonization measures, and one at the end to critically reflect on our findings and validate the potential acceptability of the policy packages analyzed. A continuous dialogue between the research team and a Stakeholder Board (SB), representing key Austrian institutions, ensured the refinement of the policy measures integrated into the analysis and model simulations.

The following sections provide a detailed documentation of the methods used (see section 2) and the results of the stakeholder workshops and the SB dialogue (see section 3). We highlight the integration of stakeholder knowledge in the project (see section 4) and end with conclusions (see section 5).

2 Methods

2.1 Dialogue with the Stakeholder Board (SB)

Establishing an ongoing stakeholder dialogue is always a challenging task, especially in projects that run over many years, such as **TransFair-AT**, which had a total duration of three years (November 2021 to October 2024). To facilitate a continuous stakeholder integration and dialogue, we therefore established a Stakeholder Board (SB), consisting of six key stakeholders from the administration (Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Federal Ministry for Social Affairs, Environment Agency Austria), NGOs (Caritas, VCÖ), and interest groups (Chamber of Labor). The SB provided valuable feedback at three critical stages:

- Project Proposal Review (Kick-off meeting, February 1st, 2022)
- Vulnerable Household Analysis: Feedback on proposed household types, initial vulnerability results, and potential case studies (April 26th, 2023)
- Preliminary Model Results and Policies: Review of simulated policy measures (May 14th, 2024)

All SB meetings took place online, which ensured a more active attendance in the meetings. All SB members were also invited to participate in the interactive workshops and were given the opportunity for bilateral meetings. While many SB members did participate in the workshops, none requested bilateral meetings. SB members were always provided with the slides and minutes from the SB meetings.

At the kick-off meeting, SB members were introduced to the project and key issues were discussed, specifically regarding (i) stakeholder participation and (ii) aspects to be considered in the project that had not been addressed so far. The SB members were invited to participate in the first interactive stakeholder workshop (see section 2.2; three attended, one sent a replacement, one was sick, and one could not attend) and were sent an update in July on the project progress with the possibility of providing feedback to us.

In the second SB meeting, we discussed (1) the classification of vulnerable household types including first results; (2) first results regarding vulnerability and mobility; and (3) potential case studies for vulnerable households. In July and September 2023, the SB received an update regarding modelling linkages and model simulations via email.

In the third SB meeting, SB members were asked to (1) critically evaluate the main findings of the model simulations regarding social impacts and to (2) discuss which compensation measures could best alleviate negative social impacts.

2.2 First interactive stakeholder workshop

The first interactive stakeholder workshop (March 31st, 2022) was organized as an interactive online workshop due to COVID restrictions at that time, inviting key stakeholders from Austrian NGOs, public administration, advocacy groups, and research institutions. The pre-selection was done based on the expertise of the project team and the recommendations of the SB. 32 invitations were sent out to pre-selected staff from NGOs, administration, advocacy groups and research institutions, of which 18 actively attended and participated in the online workshop.

The first workshop focused on two objectives:

- (1) Identification and ranking of categories for characterizing vulnerable households, and
- (2) Proposing and prioritizing effective climate policies and accompanying compensation measures, including their perceived advantages and disadvantages.

To ensure seamless and constructive online engagement, we made use of the online meeting software Zoom and its survey function as well as the online platform *miro*. The latter allows participants to contribute ideas and comments collaboratively on a virtual whiteboard. The voting system in Zoom and the *miro* boards were created in advance and tested for usability by the project team. Overall, the workshop was structured around two interactive parts, in which the participants had to carry out different tasks. While the first task was conducted in a plenary and focused on the first objective, i.e. vulnerable households, participants were split into two groups

(i.e. housing and mobility) for the second part, which focused on the second objective, i.e. climate mitigation and compensation measures.

2.2.1 Identification and ranking of categories and indicators for characterizing vulnerable households

The workshop started with an introductory presentation on household type indicators (15 minutes). During the presentation, the participants were encouraged to rate the presented household type indicators according to their applicability for measuring vulnerability to climate change policies, using Zoom's survey function. Unfortunately, some of the survey data was lost after the workshop (questions on the mobility situation). However, we sent out an online survey after the workshop to allow participants to rate these household type indicators again. The response rate to this survey was very high (72%).

After this introduction, the survey participants were asked to generate ideas for other potential household type categories and indicators that could be used to assess vulnerability to climate mitigation policies (in addition to those from the presentation and the survey). This exercise allowed participants to familiarise themselves with the miro boards. All but one participant were able to work with the miro boards without any problems. This was therefore a good preparation for the next task, which involved considerable interaction with the miro boards.

2.2.2 Proposing and prioritizing effective climate policies and accompanying compensation measures

The second task was the main focus of the workshop and focused on climate mitigation and compensation measures for the mobility and housing sectors. Based on their expertise and interest, participants were divided into two groups and given access to either a mobility or a housing miro board. These boards differed only in title, but not in design. Two hours, including breaks, were devoted to this task, which involved three steps:

1. Brainstorming phase: At the beginning, participants were given the task of identifying potential climate mitigation measures under the categories "taxes & duties", "legal framework", "regulation", "bans", "information, consulting, training", "spatial planning", "infrastructure" or "investment subsidies".
2. Ranking the measures: After the brainstorming phase, participants could rank the importance of the climate mitigation measures.
3. Discussing the pros and cons: During a break, the facilitators would identify 4-6 of the highest ranked measures (taking into account duplication of measures or merging of very similar measures). These measures were then discussed within the group and participants could add their pros and cons or general discussion points to the miro board.

These steps were then repeated for the identification of accompanying compensation measures. The only difference was the use of different categories, i.e. "reduction of taxes and duties", "transfers", "contributions in-kind", "infrastructure and supply", "investment subsidies".

After the workshop, the results and findings were consolidated, summarised and sent to all stakeholders who had expressed interest in the project (about 40 people). We also included a link to a survey so that people could provide additional feedback on the outcomes of the workshop, including questions such as: "Are there any other indicators / climate mitigation measures / compensation measures not mentioned so far that should be considered?", as well as general feedback. We received some useful feedback from this survey (see sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2).

2.3 Second interactive stakeholder workshop

The second and final interactive stakeholder workshop (June 6th, 2024) served two main purposes:

1. Validation of Model Results: Stakeholders were presented with the model simulation results and given the opportunity to critically review the simulation results.
2. Identification of Measures for Hardship Cases: Two working groups were asked to address specific challenges.

In the first part of the workshop, the results of the economic, mobility and building model were presented by the project team and then discussed with stakeholders in a plenary session. Each presentation lasted approximately 13 minutes, followed by approximately 10 minutes of discussion. Stakeholders were also provided with printed documents containing a list of measures considered in the model simulations and model results.

In the second part of the workshop, options for mitigating social hardship during the transition were discussed with stakeholders in two separate groups. Group 1 focused on car dependency and people with disabilities. Group 2 addressed the needs of elderly people living alone in single-family homes and car-dependent households at risk of poverty. Each group was moderated by a member of the research team with facilitation experience, and we ensured that a representative from each modelling team was present in the groups to answer specific questions. Flipcharts were used to collect ideas and comments from stakeholders. Guiding questions were used to stimulate lively discussion. Finally, the groups presented a summary of their discussions and findings to the plenary.

3 Results

The results of the workshop and the SB dialogue are presented in chronological order. Section 4 provides information on how stakeholder knowledge and recommendations were incorporated into the analysis and model simulations.

3.1 First SB meeting (2022-02-01)

It was important to some SB members that the project team consider – or at least discuss – individual vulnerable groups, such as people with disabilities and asylum seekers. While the modelling framework used in this project does not allow for such detailed analysis, we wanted to discuss and address this issue in the forthcoming workshops and publications as qualitative case studies. As shown in section 3.5, we included this proposal in our second and final workshop. We also addressed the issue of vulnerable groups in our Research Brief #2 (Pfaffenbichler et al., 2023).

In terms of other aspects, the SB members recommended looking at best practices from other countries and taking into account the many different aspects of energy poverty (e.g. not only income but also living conditions). They also provided us with a list of potential stakeholders for our first stakeholder workshop.

3.2 First interactive stakeholder workshop (2022-03-31)

3.2.1 Characteristics of vulnerable households

Table 3-1 below shows the results of the Zoom survey in the first stakeholder workshop on categories / indicators to characterize vulnerable households. Overall, participants were fairly satisfied with the indicators proposed by the research team, with most scoring between good (2) and satisfactory (3).

Table 3-1. Survey on: How well does the following indicator characterise an affected household with regard to the selected category? Answer selection: 1 (very good) to 5 (not at all)

Category	Indicator	Average	Number of answers
Income	Available household income	2.2	18
Energy poverty	Energy costs as a share of income	2.5	18
	Qualitative indicators (affordable, pleasantly warm)	1.9	18
Mobility situation	Rural region	2.3	13
	Car available	2.8	13
	Access to public transportation	2.2	13
Living situation	Tenure status (e.g. ownership, rent...)	2.3	18
	Number of apartments	2.7	18
	Year of construction	3.1	18

Stakeholders came up with many ideas for additional categories and indicators to be used, particularly in relation to energy poverty, mobility, housing condition, income, work, health and age (see Figure 3-1). One issue that emerged from this task was that data availability often limits the use of appropriate indicators (e.g. hidden energy poverty, time poverty, availability of driving licences). And while many participants preferred qualitative indicators, these are very difficult to assess objectively/quantitatively (e.g. what is an “adequate” room temperature? When is access to public transport “good”?). The main lessons for the project team from this task were therefore:

- Consider the share of fossil fuel costs.
- Include socio-demographic elements in the case studies (qualitative).
- Do not use year of construction (housing) and car availability as indicators.

Figure 3-1: Brainstorming ideas for household types

In addition, the survey sent out after the first workshop gave us some more useful comments on household type indicators:

- We should look at the primary and secondary indicators of the EU Energy Poverty Observatory (EPOV).
- Look at socio-economic parameters in addition to income.
- Consider potential indicators of mobility vulnerability, such as: access to car sharing; access to regional centres and workplaces.

3.2.2 Climate mitigation and compensation measures

Stakeholders provided a wealth of valuable information that significantly influenced the design of our policy packages. The results for the mobility sector are summarised in Table 3-2 (mitigation measures) and Table 3-3 (compensation measures). The results for the housing sector are summarised in Table 3-4 (mitigation measures) and Table 3-5 (compensation measures). Figure A-3 to Figure A-8 in Appendix “A.1 Results of the first stakeholder workshop” illustrate the many ideas and discussions generated by the participants with the miro boards.

With regard to **private mobility**, the three most important mitigations measures according to our participants were:

- 1) Tax measures are expected to have a large impact, but require compensatory measures and are politically difficult to implement.
- 2) Expansion of non-motorized individual transport and public transport is seen as a prerequisite for the transformation, but remains expensive and will require substantial subsidies.
- 3) Spatial planning measures.

Other measures include road tolls, education, bans on fossil fuel vehicles and speed limits.

To compensate for the potential negative social impacts of these measures, stakeholders specifically recommended:

- a) Increased investment in public transport, which could increase acceptance but requires long-term planning and substantial financing,
- b) a lump-sum transfer similar to the climate bonus (“Klimabonus”) currently implemented in Austria, but with improved social targeting; and
- c) making public transport cheaper or free.

Other measures included a reduction in VAT and an eco-social reform of the commuter allowance.

In terms of **housing**, the three most important mitigation measures according to our participants were:

- 1) A ban on fossil fuel heating systems is seen as very effective, but there are issues of acceptability and feasibility.
- 2) Changes in legislation.
- 3) Infrastructure improvements.

Other measures included subsidies, taxes, a retrofitting obligation, training of qualified personnel, and limiting the maximum living space per person.

To compensate for the potential negative social impacts of these measures, stakeholders specifically recommended:

- a) to provide lump-sum transfers, even if they are not perfectly socially targeted,
- b) to promote a phase-out of fossil fuel across district boundaries, and
- c) to introduce rent neutrality.

Other measures included social milieu protection against gentrification and strengthening consumer rights.

The **general discussion** highlighted the importance of timing and context. Participants felt that the success of climate change mitigation depends on a good mix of measures, such as carbon pricing and the expansion of public transport. There was some disagreement among participants about the acceptability, cost and impact of the selected measures.

In addition, the survey sent out after the first workshop provided us with some more useful comments on measures in the mobility sector, such as:

- Climate mitigation: a mobility budget, tax benefits for shared mobility
- Compensation measures: integrated approach to settlement development and property management

Table 3-2. Climate mitigation measures for private mobility – points, pros and cons by participants

Measure	Points	Pros	Cons
Tax measures	9	Large impact	Needs compensation measures; people do not always consider costs; social compensation difficult; political effort high
Expansion of non-motorised individual transport and public transport	8	Financial and health benefits; necessary for the transformation	Expensive; NIMBY; not possible to cover costs without subsidies
Spatial planning measures	6	No discussion	
Road toll	4	Takes into account other externalities; clear impact and boundaries	Maybe counter-productive; technical effort high (MÖSt easier)
Education	4	No discussion	
Ban on fossil-fuelled vehicles	4	Breaking the lock-in; increases pressure on manufacturers; value creation and employment potential	"paternalistic", noise & space consumption remain
Speed limit	3	Socially just; cheap; less noise and higher quality of life	Low acceptance; impact low; must be controlled

Table 3-3. Compensation measures for private mobility – points, pros and cons by participants

Measure	Points	Pros	Cons
Increase investments in public transportation	8	Seen by some as a great lever to create more acceptance for climate protection	Long planning time and the high investment requirement of these measures
Eco-bonus	6	Socially just compensation	The accuracy of the eco-bonus was questioned by some; current implementation of the eco-bonus is criticised
Make public transportation cheaper / free of charge	6	No discussion	
Reduce VAT	4	No discussion	
Eco-social reform of commuter allowance	4	An ecological reform of the commuter allowance would also counteract urban sprawl	Reform of commuter subsidies is a "sacred political cow"; the ecological effect is also doubted

Table 3-4. Climate mitigation measures for private housing – points, pros and cons by participants

Measure	Points	Pros	Cons	General
Ban on fossil fuel heating systems	7	Seen by many as effective measures to achieve climate goals, with long-term orientation	Possible financing problems; acceptance and feasibility of such bans difficult	Renovation rate still needs to be defined
Change legal requirements	6	No discussion		
Infrastructure improvements	5	No discussion		
Subsidies	4	No discussion		
Taxes	4	No discussion		
Renovation obligation	4	No discussion		
Training of qualified personnel	2	Could be an employment booster, allows for retraining	Requires long lead times	
Limitation of the maximum living space per person	2		Difficult to reconcile with the fundamental right to property	Already implemented in non-profit housing

Table 3-5. Compensation measures for private housing – points, pros and cons by participants

Measure	Points	Pros	Cons	General
Transfers	11	Fulfil several objectives at the same time; high efficiency in administration	May not be accurate for particularly affected households	
Promote fossil fuel phase-out	6			Should be planned across district boundaries
Rent neutrality	4			
Social milieu protection against gentrification	3	Berlin example: preemptive rights of the municipality	Implementation is seen as difficult	
Strengthening consumer rights	2	Could lead to more acceptance	Not quite clear which obligations & restrictions appear with the choice of an energy source; e.g. district heating connection, ban on fossil energy sources	

3.3 Second SB meeting (2023-04-26)

The discussion on the classification of vulnerable household types covered issues such as:

- Qualitative characteristics
- Heating systems considered
- Ownership / tenure issues
- Income perspectives (unrealized expenses)
- Income threshold for "vulnerable income situation"
 - Stakeholders largely agreed with our definition (max. 140% of the equivalent median income)
 - The Federal Ministry of Social Affairs uses 60% of the equivalent median income for its "Wohnschirm" programme, but they agree that a higher threshold is useful for our approach

Regarding vulnerability and mobility, stakeholders urged us to match household types with their access to public transport, referring to qualitative categories already developed by the Environment Agency Austria.

We also received many suggestions for possible case studies of vulnerable households, i.e. to consider

- the concerns and needs of women;
- that each situation is unique;
- the many trade-offs involved in climate mitigation measures;

- the lack of resources for subsidies;
- approaches that combine affordable housing with energy efficiency criteria;
- the differences between federal states.

3.4 Third SB meeting (2024-05-14)

In the third SB meeting, SB members were able to discuss preliminary results of our model simulations, particularly in relation to social impacts and what compensation measures are needed to mitigate negative social impacts.

With regard to climate mitigation measures, the SB members made the following comments:

- Concerning the timing of the introduction of the road toll, we need to find a trade-off between realism and target effectiveness.
- It would be helpful to provide a calculation of specific additional costs for households in the mobility sector (case studies).
- Resistance is to be expected if private households are obliged to renovate.
- Possible measure: Obligation to renovate except for private households
 - *Response from the research team:* Unfortunately, this is beyond the scope of our modelling.
- Higher housing costs: A breakdown of operating costs and investment costs would be helpful for the presentation.

With regard to compensation measures, the SB members made the following comments:

- Is it possible to apply a social differentiation of the road toll?
 - *Response:* Difficult to implement in practice and in the modelling framework.
- Introduction of a subsidy for low-income households to switch from internal combustion engines to electric cars.
 - *Response:* This requires research into the potential; alternative measures: leasing model for low-income households that do not have public transport nearby.
- Subsidies for low-income households: Important issues are pre-financing and ensuring quick and reliable verification of eligibility.
 - *Response:* Correct, but these aspects are difficult to include in the modelling simulations; this will be discussed in the final workshop.
- Solutions for rural areas are needed, e.g. car-pooling.
- When expanding public transport in rural areas: It is important to do this in coordination with businesses (e.g. to fit in with business hours).
- When practical solutions are offered, there is also demand – e.g. replacement of appliances or boilers.

3.5 Second interactive stakeholder workshop (2024-06-20)

3.5.1 Model results

Overall, stakeholders largely validated the results of the model simulations and made only minor suggestions for policy refinement. Regarding our policy scenarios, they mainly requested some clarification on subsidies in the building sector and why we included more measures in the private mobility sector (answer: because this sector requires more action). With regard to our model results (see Kettner et al., 2025; Pfaffenbichler et al., 2024), the following questions were discussed and answered by the research team¹:

Macroeconomic results

- Is the income gap between income quintiles increasing in absolute terms?
 - Yes, this is due to the large employment effect from which higher incomes benefit more.
- How is the car industry taken into account?
 - All sectors are considered and react in the model
 - However, the car industry is strongly export-oriented – exports do not change because the macroeconomic model DYNK only represents Austria; assumptions would have to be made about changes in the exporting countries.
- Differentiated consideration of income effects makes sense – why do higher income quintiles benefit more?
 - Income is broken down into different categories (wages/transfers etc.). This differentiation was considered and reported in the final model simulation (Kettner et al., 2025).
- Can household wealth be represented?
 - Unfortunately, there are no data on household wealth at the detailed household level.

Private mobility sector

- How much energy will be needed for passenger transport in 2040?
 - This has not yet been evaluated, but we will consider it in the final reports and documentation. The evaluation after the workshop showed the following: motorized individual transport requires about 40 TWh in 2022. In the Reference Scenario (REF) it decreases to about 25 TWh in 2040. In the policy scenarios (DECARB & COMP) it decreases to about 10 TWh in 2040.
- New approaches are needed for mobility poor households without infrastructure in rural areas, e.g. home office.
 - Rural areas are the problem, where the failures of spatial planning in recent decades are cumulative.
 - The detailed analysis of households is still limited to individual examples from rural and intermediate areas, but it is planned to assess the mobility of most of the 37 mobility poor households in the database in an upcoming publication.

¹ Model results were also discussed with research experts in a separate workshop (Pfaffenbichler et al., 2024).

- Does the 50% expansion of public transport include new lines?
 - The MARS model does not include allocation to specific routes and therefore does not directly map individual lines. The model uses aggregated information on public transport services per origin-destination pair. The model assumptions can be interpreted as both frequency increases and the creation of new lines.
- Could the 50% expansion of public transport be distributed differently from region to region?
 - This would be possible in principle, but relatively complex. A certain minimum level of service could be defined to be achieved in all types of areas.

Housing sector

- Is there a difference between cooperatives and private landlords in apartment buildings?
 - There are different approaches to organizing the distribution of costs.
- Does the model show only energy prices or total energy costs?
 - All energy costs are included in the model.
 - For example, large increases in network costs for gas will not be shown if there are fewer consumers on the network.

3.5.2 Hardship cases

Stakeholders provided valuable insights into potential hardship cases and how to mitigate them. Suggestions from Group 1, which focused on the hardship case of “car dependency and people with disabilities”, included:

- Mobility planning in businesses
- Carpooling initiatives and targeted financial support for low-income households
- Linking retrofitting funding to living space per person (m²/person)
- Combining energy advice with social support to improve outreach
- Revising §18 MRG to ensure that rent increases after retrofitting remain “warm rent neutral”
- Reintroduce rent subsidies
- Improve consumer protection for district heating

Proposals from Group 2, which addressed the needs of the hardship cases “elderly people living alone in single-family homes” and “car-dependent households at risk of poverty”, included:

- Establishment of a “Transformation Agency” to support individuals in the transition to sustainable housing and mobility
- Promoting of cultural change in housing to increase flexibility
- Correcting past spatial planning errors by improving public transport access to social housing

While these discussions went beyond the scope of our modelling approach, they provided valuable insights and broadened the range of policy options for reducing vulnerability. It was interesting to note that the question we initially proposed for the group work “Which hardship cases are particularly challenging to address?” was seen

as conceptually flawed by Group 2, who felt that there would most likely always be a solution to any hardship case.

4 Integration of stakeholder knowledge in the analysis and model simulations

4.1 Integration into the analysis of vulnerable household types

For the final analysis of vulnerable households (Bock-Schappelwein and Kettner, 2024, 2023), we were able to incorporate several suggestions from stakeholders and SB members:

- For the “income vulnerability” category, we used the recommended indicator of max. 140% of the equivalent median income. This was discussed at length, particularly in the second SB meeting (see section 3.3).
- For “energy vulnerability”, we used a mixture of the quantitative indicator “use of fossil fuels at home” and the qualitative indicator “perceived unaffordability of keeping the home adequately warm”. Both were recommended in the first stakeholder workshop (see section 3.2.1), taking into account stakeholders’ slightly different preferences for quantitative and qualitative indicators.
- For “housing vulnerability”, we specifically used either “household living in rented accommodation” or “household living in multi-family houses” as an indicator. Residential relationships were considered an important indicator in the first stakeholder workshop (see section 3.2.1).
- Finally, for “mobility vulnerability” we used the indicator “household living in regions with poor public transport quality”, which required matching household types with public transport categories – a strong recommendation from the SB members in the second meeting (see section 3.3).

4.2 Integration into the model simulations

Table 4-1 shows that we successfully simulated most of the measures proposed and approved during the first workshop (see section 3.2.2).

Private mobility sector

In the mobility sector models, we implemented all the *climate mitigation measures* recommended by stakeholders in the first workshop, except for those that were beyond the scope of our modelling framework, i.e. spatial planning measures (3rd rank) and education (5th rank). Tax measures, the most highly ranked mitigation measure by stakeholders, were implemented through carbon pricing, an increase in the mineral oil tax and the introduction of parking fees. The second most important mitigation measure, the expansion of non-motorized individual transport and public transport, was implemented through the promotion of active mobility and mobility management, and the improvement of public transport and non-motorized individual transport services. In addition, road tolls were introduced (4th rank), the share of battery electric vehicles was increased (6th rank: ban on fossil fuel vehicles), and a speed limit was introduced (7th and last rank).

With the exception of a reduction in VAT (4th rank), we implemented all the *compensation measures* recommended by stakeholders in the first workshop. The improvement of public transport and non-motorized individual transport services can be seen as equivalent to an increase in investment in public transport (1st rank). We introduced a climate bonus (2nd rank: lump sum transfers) that is only eligible up to a certain household income level (the first three out of five income quintiles), taking into account the stakeholders’ recommendation to make

the climate bonus more progressive in its effect². We reduced the price of public transport tickets by 50% (3rd rank: making public transport cheaper) and we have greened the commuter allowance (5th rank) and made it more socially targeted by making it eligible only up to a certain household income level (the same threshold as the climate bonus).

Housing sector

Similarly to the private mobility sector, we were able to implement all of the *climate mitigation measures* recommended in the first workshop in the housing sector model, except for two that were outside the scope of our modelling framework, i.e. a change in legislation (2nd rank) and training of qualified personnel (7th rank). A ban on fossil fuel heating systems (1st rank) was implemented by not allowing liquid or solid fossil fuels in new buildings and by banning the operation of fossil fuel heating systems. Infrastructure improvements (3rd rank) were introduced through many measures in the housing sector model: thermal retrofitting, increased energy efficiency, higher retrofitting rates and quality of new buildings. Subsidies (4th rank) were introduced through higher subsidy budgets and socially differentiated subsidy rates. In the case of the socially differentiated climate bonus, this is in line with stakeholders' recommendation to make the compensation more socially targeted. Tax measures (5th rank) are taken into account through the carbon tax. The implemented model measure of higher retrofitting rates and quality of new buildings somewhat reflects the recommendation for a renovation obligation (6th rank). Finally, we introduced a limited expansion of living space, which reflects the recommendation to limit the maximum living space per person.

In terms of *compensation measures*, we were able to implement the two most highly ranked measures from the first workshop: transfers (1st rank) via the socially differentiated subsidy rate and the promotion of the phasing-out of fossil fuels (2nd rank) via separate funding pots for detached two-family houses (TFH) and multi-family houses (MFH). Accounting for rent neutrality (3rd rank), social milieu protection against gentrification (4th rank) and strengthening consumer rights (5th rank) were outside the scope of the housing sector model.

General remarks

Measures excluded from the model simulations were generally outside the scope of the modelling framework. Examples include education and training initiatives, changes in legislation, measures to ensure rent neutrality, protecting of social milieus against gentrification, and strengthening consumer rights. A notable exception was the suggestion to reduce VAT, which we replaced with a climate bonus transfer. The latter has been shown in previous studies to be a more progressive and thus more socially targeted approach to recycling carbon tax revenues (Kettner et al., 2024; Kirchner et al., 2019; Mayer et al., 2021).

² However, we were not able to implement the regional differentiation applied to the Austrian climate bonus.

Table 4-1. Outcomes of the stakeholder workshop

Sector	Category	Measures proposed by stakeholders	Pts ¹	REF ²	CLIM ²	COMP ²	Measures implemented in the scenarios
Mobility	Mitigation	Tax measures	9	Yes	Yes	Yes	CO ₂ pricing Mineral oil tax increase Parking fees
		Expansion of non-motorized individual transport and public transport	8	Yes	Yes	Yes	Promotion of active mobility & mobility management Improvement of public transport & non-motorized individual transport services
		Spatial planning measures	6	No	No	No	
		Road toll	4	No	Yes	Yes	Introduction of distance-based road toll
		Education	4	No	No	No	
		Ban on fossil-fueled vehicles	4	No	Yes	Yes	Share of BEV increases
		Speed limit	3	No	Yes	Yes	
	Compensation	Increase investments in public transportation	8	No	Yes	Yes	Improvement of public transport & non-motorized individual transport services
		Eco-bonus	6	No	No	Yes	Climate bonus for Q1-Q3
		Make public transportation cheaper / free of charge	6	No	No	Yes	50% reduction of the public transport ticket price
Reduce VAT		4	No	No	No		
Eco-social reform of commuter allowance		4	No	Yes	Yes	Greening of commuter allowance	
Housing	Mitigation	Ban on fossil fuel heating systems	7	No	Yes	Yes	No liquid & solid fossil fuels in new buildings Operating ban on fossil fuel heating systems
		Change legal requirements	6	No	No	No	
		Infrastructure improvements	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Thermal refurbishment Increasing energy efficiency Higher retrofitting rates and qualities of new buildings
		Subsidies	4	No	No	Yes	Higher funding budgets Socially differentiated subsidy rates
		Tax measures	4	Yes	Yes	Yes	CO ₂ pricing
		Renovation obligation	4	No	Yes	Yes	Higher retrofitting rates and qualities of new buildings
		Training of qualified personnel	2	No	No	No	
		Limitation of the maximum living space per person	2	No	Yes	Yes	Limited expansion of living space
	Compensation	Transfers	11	No	No	Yes	Socially differentiated subsidy rates
		Promote fossil fuel phase-out	6	No	Yes	Yes	Separate funding pots for detached TFH and MFH
		Rent neutrality	4	No	No	No	
		Social milieu protection against gentrification	3	No	No	No	
		Strengthening consumer rights	2	No	No	No	

¹ Each stakeholder was given three points, which they could assign to the most important measures

² REF refers to the reference scenario, CLIM refers to the climate mitigation scenario and COMP refers to CLIM plus compensation measure scenario (see Kettner et al., 2025).

5 Conclusions

The stakeholder integration process was instrumental in ensuring the relevance, robustness and practicality of our project outcomes. By engaging stakeholders throughout the project, we incorporated critical feedback, simulated stakeholder-supported policies, and explored broader solutions to effectively address hardship cases and reduce vulnerability.

We successfully incorporated several suggestions from stakeholders, such as refining income thresholds for vulnerable household types, aligning household types with public transport categories, and improving the presentation of results. Our model simulations were able to incorporate many of the stakeholder recommendations on both climate mitigation measures and compensation measures. Stakeholder input also highlighted challenges beyond our modelling approach, including detailed case studies of vulnerable households and barriers to policy implementation.

A key aim of integrating stakeholder knowledge was to increase the potential acceptance of climate mitigation and compensation measures in our policy scenarios. While we succeeded in engaging a diverse group of stakeholders, it was not fully representative of the Austrian population. Engaging a representative sample of stakeholders remains a challenge even in cases that explicitly attempt to do so, such as the Austrian climate assembly (“Klimarat”)³ (Buzogány et al., 2022; Ehs and Praprotnik, 2023). Surveys show that the majority of Austrian citizens support climate mitigation measures (Eckert et al., 2024). However, specific measures such as speed limits, wind power projects and compensation schemes such as the climate bonus remain the subject of intense debate in the Austrian media and politics. Despite a growing body of research on how to effectively communicate climate mitigation science to the public and decision-makers, as well as studies on the acceptability of these measures, further research efforts are needed to better understand the barriers to implementation and to develop improved measures and strategies to overcome them.

³Our summary from the first workshop was used as knowledge input for the “Klimarat”. We were approached by one stakeholder, who participated in the scientific evaluation team in the Austrian “Klimarat” (climate council), and asked if they could use our workshop summary as knowledge input.

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A. Annex

A.1 Results of the first stakeholder workshop

Note for all figures below: Clustering and colouring was done after the workshop. In some cases, post-it texts were slightly changed but only to improve readability, not by changing their content and intent.

Figure A-1: Brainstorming and ranking ideas for climate mitigation measures in the sector private mobility

Klimaschutzmaßnahmen - Mobilität Vor- & Nachteile

Ergebnisse Vor- und Nachteile ausgewählter Mobilitätsklimaschutzmaßnahmen

Vorteil Anmerkung Nachteil
Kommentar / Ergänzung zum Post-it darüber

anreiz-kompatibel	Generiert Ein-nahmen	Pendler-pauschale höherer Bereich	schnell wirksam	Belastet höhere Einkommen	wirksam, aber braucht begleitende Maßnahmen	CO2 Preis muss hoch genug sein	Steuer-system	Kontext wichtig	Reform der Pendler-pauschale	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	erhöhten Netto-ökonomisch	keine Anreize kann gegeben werden	große administrative & bürokratische Aufwand		
verwend-bar	sozial, ökologisch & ökonom.	deutliches Signal	insgesamt bei MFAktiv, da mehr Wettbewerb	auslösen bei MFAktiv, da mehr Wettbewerb	Ausbau ÖV, soziale Vergünstigung	im Lenkungs-wirkung zu erreichen	Angestrebter Wirkung und sozialer Ausgleich	Ziel: Ökologisch und sozial gerecht	vermutlich wenig Feinregulierung	auf politischer Ebene, wie viele Änderungen können man bei den anderen	vermutlich wenig Feinregulierung	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	ggfs. Kontraproduktiv	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse
Substi-tutions-möglichkeit	Andere Prio-rierung	positive finanzielle Bilanz	senkt Emissionen und steigert Gesundheit	Gut, aber es braucht Wende in den Köpfen	Nachfrage für Public-Mobility gegen MIV	sehr wirksam, aber nicht schnell umsetzbar	Ausbau nicht-MIV & ÖV	Arbeitsbedingungen relevant (ÖV)	oft nicht kosten-deckend möglich	teuer	OM Ausbau vs. NIMBY	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	ggfs. Kontraproduktiv	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse
ermöglicht neues Denken	durch aktive Mobilität	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken
sozial gerecht	kosten-günstig	weniger Feinstaub	weniger Lärm	hohe CO2 Einsparungspotenzial	nur für fossile	wird attraktiver	Tempolimits	IG-Luft trifft nur Verbrenner	akzeptanz gering	Wirkung nicht groß genug	Bringt nicht viel	muss kontrolliert werden	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse
schnell wirksam	T30-mehr Lebens-qualität	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken	ermöglicht neues Denken
Durch-trichter des fossilen Lock-in	wichtig den festzulegen, damit planbar	neues we-sentliches & bewährtes Element	Wichtig um Innovation an Board zu holen	erhöht Druck auf Hersteller	wichtige Signal für Entscheidungsteilnehmer	Voraus-setzungen für ÖV Ausbau relevant	Verbot fossilbetriebe Fahrzeuge	Zeitraum relevant	Wert-schöpfung-kenn-lich Arbeitmarkt	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse
Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse	Rechen-pauschale für viele und Mittelklasse

Figure A-2: Pros and Cons of highly-ranked climate mitigation measures in the sector private mobility

Kompensationsmaßnahmen - Mobilität

Ergebnis der Ideensammlung für Kompensationsmaßnahmen im Bereich Klimaschutz-Mobilität

Zusammen-gefasstes Maßnahmenbündel
Stimmen 0 1 2 3
detaillierter Kommentar zu Vorschlag im Post-it darüber

Figure A-3: Brainstorming and ranking ideas for compensation measures in the sector private mobility

Klimaschutzmaßnahmen - Gebäude Vor- & Nachteile

Ergebnisse Vor- und Nachteile ausgewählter Gebäudeklimaschutzmaßnahmen

Vorteil		Anmerkung		Nachteil		Kommentar / Ergänzung zum Post. 4 darüber				
Erreichung Klimanutralität bis 2040	Effektive THP-Emissionsvermeidung	Erde bleibt für Menschen bewohnbar	Ermöglicht klare langfristige Orientierung	Trend würde fortgesetzt werden	Fossile Wärmequellen im Neubau verboten	Timing der Verbote hochkomplex	Grünes Gas Argument	Frühzeitbarkeit i.U. nicht gegeben	Anstieg Nicht-CO2 Emissionen	
Erreichung Klimanutralität bis 2040	Effektive THP-Emissionsvermeidung	Erde bleibt für Menschen bewohnbar	Ermöglicht klare langfristige Orientierung	Trend würde fortgesetzt werden	Fossile Wärmequellen im Bestand verboten	Timing der Verbote hochkomplex	Grünes Gas Argument	Frühzeitbarkeit i.U. nicht gegeben	Anstieg Nicht-CO2 Emissionen	
Erreichung Klimanutralität bis 2040	Effektive THP-Emissionsvermeidung	Reduktion Primärenergieverbrauch	Ermöglicht klare langfristige Orientierung	Sanierung muss nicht bis auf die letzte Generation sein	Sanierungspflicht abhängig von thermischer Qualität	Timing der Verbote hochkomplex	Wer finanziert dies?	Wer kann eine solche Pflicht umsetzen?	Viele fühlen sich angegriffen	Wann gibt es ein Gebäude als saniert?
Umkehrung von Vorzeichen, die nicht mehr "gebraucht" werden				Beschäftigungsbörsen	Ausbildung qualifiziertes Personal	Lange Vorlaufzeit				

Figure A-6: Pros and Cons of highly-ranked climate mitigation measures in the sector private housing

Kompensationsmaßnahmen - Gebäude

Ergebnis der Ideensammlung für Kompensationsmaßnahmen im Bereich Klimaschutz-Mobilität

Figure A-7: Brainstorming and ranking ideas for compensation measures in the sector private housing

Kompensationsmaßnahmen - Gebäude Vor- & Nachteile
 Ergebnisse Vor- und Nachteile ausgewählter Kompensationsmaßnahmen im Bereich Gebäude

Vor-
teil
Anmer-
kung
Nach-
teil
Kommentar
/ Ergänzung
zum Post-IT
davon

Hohe Effizienz in Verwaltung	Erfüllt mehrere Ziele gleichzeitig	Energiepreis-erhöhungen beibehalten <small>damit Reduktion stop/indere</small>	Mindestsicherung, Negativsteuern und andere bestehende Transfers erhöhen	Mehr nicht-kollektiver für HH die besonders betroffen sind <small>d.h. es breucht neben sozialer auch "sozial-fairer" Maßnahme</small>	
Kontinuierlicher Ausbau der "Gründergeneration"	Planungsleistungen für Ausstieg aus fossilen Energien fördern				
Verständliches Aufkommen gegenüber den Anwohnern / Einwohnern / Gewerbetreibenden der Kommunen <small>Beispiel: Müllabfuhr aus Berlin</small>	sozialer Milieuschutz gegen Gentrifizierung	Wie ist dies operationalisierbar?			
Mehr Akzeptanz beim Umstieg	Stärkung der Konsumentenrechte (vor allem bei Fernwärme)	Welche Prozesse gehen mit dem Umstieg einher?			

Figure A-8: Pros and Cons of highly-ranked compensation measures in the sector private housing